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Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF NURSING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICE AND BELIEF OF HAND HYGIENE

¹Palveesha Talpur, ²Muhammed Zakarya, ³Bisharat Ali

¹BScN, MPH, Nursing Instructor, Isra School of Nursing, Isra University Hospital Hyderabad, palveshatalpur@yahoo.com, ²MSN (Masters in Nursing), Nursing Instructor, ISRA University Hospital Hyderabad, mzakarya786@gmail.com, ³RN, Dip in CHN, Post RN BscN, Nursing Instructor, Isra School of Nursing, Isra University Hospital Hyderabad, bisharatali65@yahoo.com

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Abstract:

Purpose: The study was conducted descriptively to evaluate the nursing students' belief in hand hygiene, its practices and importance.

Place and Duration: In the Isra School of Nursing, Isra University Hospital Hyderabad, Pakistan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Materials and methods: The Hand Hygiene Questionnaire (HHQ) were used to collect data on personal characteristics with 13 questions. The research was conducted with 655 students who agreed to participate in the research. Data were evaluated using percentage and mean, standard deviation, independent t test and ANOVA estimation in the SPSS version 24.0 package.

Results: 64.9% of the nursing students participating in the study were female, 55.9% were in the 21-23 age group, 28.1% were in the 4th grade and 90.7% were in formal education in hand hygiene. The mean total HHQ score was 150.90 ± 12.07 and the Cronbach alpha coefficient was 0.85. Statistically, a significant difference was found between the HHQ total score averages of the students in terms of gender, age and hand hygiene education ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: We determined that the students have theoretical knowledge about hand hygiene and applied it to some extent. However, the results showed a lack of clinical practice. Students' average scores on the hand hygiene questionnaire were influenced by gender, age, and education they received. Therefore, we concluded that it would be beneficial to determine the reasons for the deficiencies in hand hygiene practices, to repeat the training periodically, to take necessary precautions and to increase student awareness.

Keywords: Hand hygiene, Knowledge, Attitude, Education, Nursing students.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Palveesha Talpur,

BScN, MPH, Nursing Instructor, Isra School of Nursing,

Isra University Hospital Hyderabad, palveshatalpur@yahoo.com,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Despite the advances in hospital services, hospital acquired infections (HI) is a major problem in the world and Pakistan. HI can cause functional impairment, emotional stress, poor quality of life, or death in patients [1-2]. Increase in hospital stay, loss of workforce and drug use, together with the use of additional diagnostic methods cause an increase in the economic burden collectively. Healthcare workers' hands are the most important way to transfer HI, and therefore hand hygiene (HH) is the most effective method of preventing nosocomial infections [1-2]. Hand hygiene is the most effective, oldest, simplest and cheapest medical method to prevent HI. It has been shown that hospital infections can be reduced by approximately 30% -50% with the application of this method. Many studies in the literature have focused on HH rates of healthcare providers. According to the study, HH rates of healthcare providers vary between 5% and 81% [3-4]. Evidence-based guidelines for general HH and specific HH measurements related to medical care have been published [5]. The most important factor in the transmission of pathogens from one patient to another by healthcare workers' hands is the absence of hand washing or hand antisepsis. Training of healthcare professionals is the most critical step in strategies to increase compliance with handwashing. In addition, regular and ongoing training programs are essential to improve compliance. Erasmus, et al., Examined 96 studies aiming at compliance with HH guidelines in patient care, and found that the compliance of healthcare personnel to HH was around 40% and that research and training were needed to increase it. Although the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and the Association of Infection Control and Epidemiologists state that hand washing is the most important method of preventing nosocomial infections, the rate of compliance with hand washing among healthcare professionals is less than 50%. Although handwashing rates differ in many studies, the common point of all research reports is that healthcare workers, especially physicians, have lower than expected handwashing rates [6-7]. The reasons behind this poor compatibility with hand washing is that hand washing behavior is not practiced. Factors that can affect individual household adjustment behavior; individual preferences of health workers, lack of knowledge in HH, professional experience, gender, perception of HH benefits, perception of the severity of infectious diseases and the role of HH in prevention [8-9]. These are work intensity, dermatological effects of HH, lack of role models etc. In this study, we set out to determine the importance of HH beliefs, HH practices and HH knowledge

among nursing students. Research questions are as follows:

- What are the students' beliefs about HD?
- In what situations do students wash their hands in clinical areas?
- How important is HH to the student?

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held in Isra School of Nursing, Isra University Hospital Hyderabad, Pakistan for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. The sample consists of 141 first year students, 158 second year students, 172 third year students and 184 fourth year students, a total of 655 participants who agreed to participate in the study.

Personal information form and a questionnaire consisting of beliefs, practices and perception of importance (HHQ) about hand hygiene were used as data collection tools. The personal information form contains questions regarding students' personal data. Personal data in the study, which was collected from a total of 12 questions, are independent variables; gender, age, years of education, longest place of residence, high school, family type, education level of parents, place of stay, hand hygiene education level and family income and expenditure status. The HBS part of the questionnaire (19 items) focused on HH belief, the HHPI section focused on the HH application inventory (14 items), and the HIS section (3 items) on HH belief. HH perception, all with 5 points. Likert type scale consists of 36 items in total. HBS items 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = not sure, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree, HHPI items 1 = never, 2 = then, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, 5 = always, HIS While the items are scaled as 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = not sure, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranges from 0.74-0.80 in the original HHQ for the HBS, HHPI, HIS sections ranging from 0.77-0.95 in the scale validity test, 0, 68-0.95 in the current study. SPSS program (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 24.0 was used for data analysis. Cronbach alpha coefficient, independent sample t test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to evaluate descriptive data. The normality test reveals a normal distribution and therefore parametric tests were used to evaluate and interpret the data. LSD multiple comparison tests were used when there was a difference between groups in Kruskal-Wallis variance analysis.

RESULTS:

The average score of the nursing students in the HBS section was 71.31 ± 6.60 , the HHPI section was 65.78 ± 6.43 , the HIS section was 13.81 ± 1.75 , and

the average total score was HHQ 150.90 ± 12.07 , which means a high score. The alpha coefficient of the questionnaire was 0.850 and the values of the sections varied between 0.688 and 0.951. 55.9% are

in the 21-23 age group. It was determined that 90.7% of the students received hand hygiene training and 88.4% received this training within the scope of the curriculum (Table 1).

Table 1 Distribution of student personal data

Variable	n	%	Variable	N	%
Living in			Hand Hygiene Education		
Alone in Family	36	5.5%	Received	594	90.7%
			Did not receive	61	9.3%
Living with family	36	5.5%			
Living with roommate	250	38.2%			
Year in Training			Source of Hand Hygiene Education		
1 st year	141	21.5%	University	579	88.4%
2 nd year	158	24.1%	Home	15	2.3%
3 rd year	172	26.3%	No education	61	9.3%
4 th year	184	28.1%			
Total	655	100.0%	Total	655	100.0%

Analysis of the data obtained from the nursing students showed that the difference between the mean scores for the BLS section ($t = -0.764$, $p = 0.445$) was not statistically significant, but the difference between the mean scores for the genders was HHPI ($t = 4.331$, p less than 0.001) and statistically significant

($p < 0.05$) for HIS (3.518 , p less than 0.001) and overall HHQ ($t = 2.373$, $p = 0.018$). While students' HHPI (66.57 ± 5.62), HBYS section (13.98 ± 1.57) and general HHQ scores (151.72 ± 11.00) were higher; HIS average of male students (71.58 ± 6.84) was found to be higher (Table 2).

Table 2 Mean score of student personal data according to HBS, HHPI, HIS, and HHQ

Variable		Section			Scale Total
		HBS	HHPI	HIS	HHQ
		$\bar{X} \pm SS$	$\bar{X} \pm SS$	$\bar{X} \pm SS$	$\bar{X} \pm SS$
Age	18-20	71.11 $\pm$ 6.12	65.43 $\pm$ 6.27	13.83 $\pm$ 1.73	150.50 $\pm$ 11.33
	21-23	71.63 $\pm$ 6.88	66.31 $\pm$ 5.99	13.77 $\pm$ 1.81	151.80 $\pm$ 11.87
	24 and above	70.41 $\pm$ 6.44	64.28 $\pm$ 8.21	13.82 $\pm$ 1.70	148.00 $\pm$ 14.19
	$\bar{X} = 21.44 \pm 1.94$				
	F-value	1.301	3.885	4.426	3.583
	p-value	0.273	0.021	0.012	0.028
Living	Alone	71.97 $\pm$ 5.19	67.19 $\pm$ 4.40	13.16 $\pm$ 2.63	152.33 $\pm$ 8.50
	With family	71.30 $\pm$ 5.91	66.80 $\pm$ 4.85	13.94 $\pm$ 1.65	152.05 $\pm$ 10.45
	With roommate	71.33 $\pm$ 6.09	65.70 $\pm$ 5.64	13.91 $\pm$ 1.46	150.95 $\pm$ 10.01
	F-value	0.120	1.632	2.368	0.758
	p-value	0.975	0.164	0.055	0.558
	Year in University	1 st year	71.02 $\pm$ 6.08	65.87 $\pm$ 6.00	14.05 $\pm$ 1.59
2 nd year		71.93 $\pm$ 6.95	65.32 $\pm$ 7.33	13.75 $\pm$ 1.82	151.01 $\pm$ 14.13
3 rd year		71.06 $\pm$ 7.17	65.50 $\pm$ 6.03	13.62 $\pm$ 1.87	150.18 $\pm$ 11.70
4 th year		71.23 $\pm$ 6.13	66.36 $\pm$ 6.27	13.84 $\pm$ 1.69	151.45 $\pm$ 11.34
F-value		0.636	0.899	1.662	0.335
p-value		0.592	0.441	0.174	0.800
Hand Hygiene Education	Received	71.32 $\pm$ 6.47	65.97 $\pm$ 6.34	13.89 $\pm$ 1.69	151.19 $\pm$ 11.91
	Did not receive	71.24 $\pm$ 7.76	64.00 $\pm$ 7.00	13.04 $\pm$ 2.06	148.29 $\pm$ 13.33
	t-value	0.088	2.361	3.743	1.843
	p-value	0.930	0.019	0.000	0.066

There were 19 questions in the HBS section of the scale and the overall mean value was 3.75. When the answers given by the nursing students to the questions were examined, it was seen that the highest score was given as "Washing hands after using the toilet can reduce the transmission of infectious diseases" with an average = 4.70. Other top scores are "Hand hygiene can protect against infection after looking at the wound" (average = 4.57), "Hand

hygiene is a habit for me in my personal life" (average = 4.53), "Prevention of diseases acquired in nosocomial infection is the role of the health worker is a valuable part" (average = 4.50). The lowest scores are "Trying to remember to do hygiene" I cannot always apply hand hygiene in recommended situations because my patient's needs come first" (average = 2.62) (Table 3).

Table 3 Mean scores for items on the hand hygiene beliefs scale

Items	Statement	Min.-Max.	$\bar{X} \pm SS$
1	I have a duty to act as a role model for other health care workers	1-5	4.30 ± 0.91
2	When busy it is more important to complete my tasks than to perform hand hygiene	1-5	2.48 ± 1.26
3	Performing hand hygiene in the recommended situations can reduce patient mortality	1-5	4.47 ± 0.71
4	Performing hand hygiene in the recommended situations can reduce medical costs associated with hospital-acquired infections	1-5	4.50 ± 0.72
5	I can't always perform hand hygiene in recommended situations because my patient's needs come first	1-5	2.62 ± 1.17
6	Prevention of hospital-acquired infection is a valuable part of a health care worker's role	1-5	4.50 ± 0.67
7	I follow the example of senior health care workers when deciding whether or not to perform hand hygiene	1-5	3.23 ± 1.27
8	I believe I have the power to change poor practices in the workplace	1-5	3.85 ± 0.92
9	Failure to perform hand hygiene in the recommended situations can be considered negligence	1-5	4.14 ± 0.94
10	Hand hygiene is a habit for me in my personal life	1-5	4.53 ± 0.64
11	I am confident I can effectively apply my knowledge of hand hygiene to my clinical practice	1-5	4.36 ± 0.78
12	It is an effort to remember to perform hand hygiene in the recommended situations	1-5	2.53 ± 1.16
13	I would feel uncomfortable reminding a health professional to hand wash	1-5	3.19 ± 1.26
14	If I disagree with a guideline, I look for research findings to guide my practice	1-5	3.99 ± 0.89
15	Performing hand hygiene slows down building immunity to disease	1-5	2.76 ± 1.35
16	Dirty sinks can be a reason for not washing hands	1-5	3.22 ± 1.22
17	Lack of an acceptable soap product can be a reason for not cleansing hands	1-5	3.28 ± 1.27
18	Performing hand hygiene after caring for a wound can protect from infections	1-5	4.57 ± 0.71
19	Cleansing hands after going to the toilet can reduce transmission of infectious disease	1-5	4.70 ± 0.58
General mean			3.75

Scale: 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

Table 4 Mean scores for items on the hand hygiene importance scale

Statement	Min.-Max.	$\bar{X} \pm SS$
1 Hand hygiene is considered an important part of the curriculum	1-5	4.59 ± 0.35
2 The facilities in which I do clinical practicum emphasize the importance of hand hygiene	1-5	4.64 ± 0.62
3 The importance of hand hygiene is emphasized	1-5	4.56 ± 0.67
General mean		4.6

Scale: 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree

There are 3 questions in the HIS section of the scale and the overall average was found to be 4.60. Examining the answers given by the nursing students to the questions, the highest score was given to the statement "The facilities where I practice clinical practice emphasize the importance of hand hygiene" (mean = 4.64). (Table 4).

DISCUSSION:

Hand washing is one of the standard measures that have been shown to be effective in reducing preventable HI. Hand hygiene is a simple procedure, but the factors affecting the compliance of healthcare professionals are quite complex. The individual characteristics of healthcare workers, working conditions (workload, availability of materials and facilities for hand hygiene, etc.) and cognitive perceptions affect compliance [9-10]. The average score of nursing students in the HHQ questionnaire was 150.90 ± 12.07 and it can create enough conspiracy. Approximately 90.7% of the nursing students participating in the study have received HH training, and the average score of the students receiving education is higher than the HHQ scale. In addition, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the HBS section and HHQ total score averages according to the education level of the students in HH ($p > 0.05$) [11-12]. It was observed that the HHPI, HIS and HHQ subscale scores of the students who received HH education in university education were higher. As a result of evaluating the mean scores of HIS, HHPI, HIS and HHQ subscales, it was concluded that nursing students had positive beliefs about hand hygiene. Keşaplı *et al.* Found that the total hand washing rate of healthcare personnel working in the emergency room was 20.3% after all contacts, and the frequency of hand washing was observed afterwards. clean contacts were statistically lower than dirty contacts. Erasmus *et al.* Systematically examined 96 studies on adherence to the HH guideline in patient care and found that healthcare staff compliance was 40% and research and training were needed for improvement. Compliance with HH. According to this information, the rate of hand washing is low among nursing students [13-14]. Beliefs about the consequences of individuals' behaviors and the value of these results are factors affecting the learning process in increasing the fulfillment of HH. Recognition of HH beliefs is believed to be particularly effective in securing students' knowledge, beliefs and practices about HH and making them appear more positive to the culture of HH practice. In the study, it was determined that the difference between HHPI, HIS and HHQ total score averages was statistically significant for age groups ($p < 0.05$). Although the average scores of the HBS, HHPI and HHQ sections of the 21-23 age group were higher than the students in the other age group, it was observed that the average total score of the HBYS section was higher. In the 18-20 age group. This finding indicates that as the students' progress in their classes, the level of awareness increases as the age gets older and more attention is

paid to household practices [15]. In this study, it was found that the average score that nursing students got from the HHPI department was higher. We could argue that students met with HH in clinical practice, but further increases are suggested. Your division means students' scores are second highest. This result shows that students are aware of the importance of HH and the value of including it in the curriculum. The average score for the HBS section was the lowest. Students' beliefs about HH need to be further improved [16].

CONCLUSION (AND RECOMMENDATIONS):

In this study, the answers given by nursing students reflect a good level of knowledge about hand washing. Despite the high theoretical knowledge on the subject, the nursing students who participated in the study were lacking in practice. In addition, it was determined that nursing students' beliefs about hand hygiene should also be improved. Further research is recommended to investigate whether nursing students will practice hand washing in clinical areas while working. It is important for academic instructors and clinical nurse instructors to keep up to date on the topic. It is thought that better conditions are needed in clinical practice, the development of checklists and related protocols, as well as a feedback mechanism to increase handwashing patterns and rates.

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